

WORK FROM HOME: FROM BEING NOT NORMAL TO NEW NORMAL

Dr. Sachin Puranik

Asst. Professor,

Satish Pradhan Dnyanasadhana College Thane

Abstract:

The entire world was affected because of corona virus which is popularly known as COVID-19. The entire world was shut down and many organisations found it difficult for survival. But knowing the patience and innovation of mankind, soon methods and measures were found out for overcoming this global crisis. Efforts from various quarters were undertaken to tackle the crisis from testing and producing vaccines to make people work from home. Work from home became a new normal and companies all around the world started their operations by making their employees stay glued to work but from home. Incentives are now being given to employees who are working from home and companies are now ready to carry on this trend in coming years.

This paper attempts to study the pros and limitations of work from home and how this trend is here to stay and how companies are giving encouragement to the same.

Key words: *Covid 19, work from home, incentives, new normal norms*

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INTRODUCTION:

One of the main behavioural changes caused by the COVID-19 pandemic has been the overnight shift to working from home phenomenon for millions of Indians. Some sectors were ready for such a kind of a situation, but many other sectors were in for a rude shock. India was locked down overnight hoping that the COVID chain will stop and India will be free from corona virus pandemic. But this did not happen, Many of small businesses found their source of income vanish in the thin air and those who were working were forced to work from home.

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Many sectors like education sector went through sweeping changes and found itself adjusting to never thought before situation of work from home

Work from has been long looked upon as an alternative in the IT sector. It has gone to such an extent in IT sector that companies are offering incentives to employees to those who are ready to work from home. But other sectors had to adopt this alternative in a hard way. Many companies started using work from home as a method or an alternative on trial and error basis. But what made it tick is the fact that lockdown was implemented strictly, vaccination drive was made compulsory, also new variants of COVID 19 made people remain indoors.

Many people lost jobs, many were made to work on part-time basis and many more were made to embrace the situation by agreeing to work from home. What made the situation even more worse was the fact that there was no formal training given to the employees and were forced to adapt to this unprecedented situation. Very little or no infrastructural support was provided by the corporate sector or by the government. It was left to the efforts of employees to show survival skills.

Today there is a situation that companies are employing a hybrid office format. This means that employees who want to work from home can do so and others can come to office for completing their work. It also means coming once in a week to office and remaining days working from home.

Work from home is longer a preferred mode of working. It is looked upon an key source of employee burnout and frustration. This is also because limited resources are being shared by both parents as well as children. Even schools and colleges are conducting lectures online. So in a family where both parents are working from home and children attending schools online, it becomes very difficult to manage the resources. So many parents prefer to go to offices rather than work from home.

There has been increase in rate of domestic abuse against women during the lockdown period. This clearly indicates that there is lack of work-life balance. There is no time frame of work and companies assume that their employees are available 24 hours. This resulted in sleep disorders and also increase in stress. The anger and frustration is generally vented on spouse and children.

Women especially whether working or otherwise, were the worst affected class because of

work from home and also online schooling.

Advantages and Limitations of Work from Home:

There are advantages and limitations of Work from Home. These are:

I. Advantages of Work from Home:

1. Better work life balance by having flexible schedule of work
2. There is no need to travel to one's workplace. This saves lot of time and also stress resulting from it.
3. No geographic restrictions. A person can take job in any company anywhere as there is no need to be physically present at workplace.
4. Work from home helps to save money which otherwise would have been spent on petrol/diesel, maintenance of vehicles, parking charges, tolls etc.
5. Less office politics, quieter place and no unproductive meetings lead to better productivity among employees.
6. Employees get to eat healthy home cooked food which leads to a healthy body and a healthy mind. This makes an employee positive and happy.

II. Limitations of voice search

1. Too many people are sharing very few resources because of work from home. This includes parents and children.
2. Distractions at home leads to less concentration and mistakes at work. This puts additional stress on the employees.
3. Since there is no face-to-face communication and no interaction with colleagues, this leads loneliness amongst employees and reduced productivity at work.
4. There is no balance between work and inadequate time with loved ones. There is no personal space for individuals.
5. There is a very high chance that an employee working from home will have a tired body and a tired mind. Burnout of employee is the main limitation of work from home.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

Literature on voice search assistants is very limited and here some research papers have been studied:

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1. **Micheal Gibbs, Friederike Mengel, Christoph Siemroth, Becker Friedman Institute, “Work from Home and Productivity: Evidence from Personnel & Analytics Data on IT Professionals” July 2021.** In this paper the researchers have studied the impact of Work from home and tried to find out limitations of work from home. This paper highlights the fact that there is very thin margin of productivity differences in work from home and work from office and an employee has to put more hours at work.
2. **Australian Government, Productivity Commission, September 2021, “Working From Home”.** This paper studies work from home trends and also the fact when now people can work from home then why weren't they working from home before. This paper also highlights the fact that in 2016 how prepared the sectors were for situation like work from home.
3. **Kirti Srivastava, Amrita Sethumadhavan, Harini Raghupathy, Shreya Agarwal, To Study the Indian Perspective on the Concept of Work from Home, February 2015, Indian Journal of Science and Technology.**

RESEARCH GAP: The above review of literature points to the fact that the studies are mainly related to finding out how it is not easy to adapt to work from home strategy for many employees due to one or the other reason. There is still a lot that needs to be done by the companies in providing physical and mental support to their employees before forcing them to work from home. Therefore, the study has been undertaken to understand the advantages and limitations of work from home.

NEED FOR THE STUDY: India is slowly and surely getting used to work from home as COVID-19 looms large with new variants. Many sectors adapted this strategy and some were successful in it whereas some other sectors like education sector faced tremendous limitations. But looking at the current trends, work from home is here is to stay and companies all around the globe are now giving incentives to their employees to stay home and work.

This study is undertaken with the following objectives which are given below.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY: The objectives of the study are to

1. To study the meaning of work from home
2. To study various advantages and limitations of work from home

METHODOLOGY:

- Sources of Data: The study is based on secondary data. The Secondary data sources include Research Articles, Websites.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY: The study tries to cover various aspects of voice search assistants like its history, advantages, functioning and limitations.

FINDINGS:

- There is a major shift in working pattern in India. People are slowly adapting to work from home method.
- There are many challenges that are there in front of employees who are forced to work from home.

SUGGESTIONS:

1. There is urgent need for training employees and also providing them with necessary for working smoothly from home.
2. The companies must provide added incentives to employees who agree to work from home.
3. Government frame policies for a situation where employees are made to work from home like working hours.

CONCLUSION:

The work from home concept is here to stay. This concept is beneficial to both the employee as well as the employer. Employees get time to spend with their loved ones and also relieve them from hectic travelling schedules and as far as employers are concerned, they save a lot of overhead expenses. So with a little effort and concern towards the employees, companies can have advantage for them through work from home. It can be looked upon as an real and workable alternative to work from office.

REFERENCES:

1. flexyjobs.com
2. Researchgate.com